

DEVELOPMENT OF SIMULATION MODEL FOR REPRODUCIBLE 3D MULTI-LAYERD WOVEN FABRICS SUITABLE IN LIGHTWEIGHT ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

Weaving of near-net-shape structures is an efficient way to produce preforms for thermoplastic glass fibre reinforced composites. To ensure the required mechanical properties of the composites, damaging of glass fibres during the weaving process has to be avoided by limitation of warp thread forces. For getting a better insight into the weaving process as well as to analyse warp thread forces under different technological parameters and machine configurations a simulation model of weaving multi-layered preforms has been developed. This enables calculations with variation of machine and process parameters to reach a minimization of the modulation of thread forces. The aim in conjunction with this is downsizing the basic tensile stress of threads for reducing fibre damage.

1 INTRODUCTION

Within the Collaborative Research Centre SFB 639 at TU Dresden a novel process chain to produce thermoplastic textile-reinforced structures with hollow spaces is developed. The process chain consists of near-net-shape weaving of spacer preforms from glass/polypropylene hybrid yarns in a single production step and subsequent hot compression-moulding to consolidated sandwich structures, Figure 1, [1-3].

Figure 1: Near-net-shape preform and composite structure

The composites with spacer-geometry can be applied in different fields such as aviation, automotive industry and transportation (e.g. as wall elements, floor panels, inner covering and isolation).

For a reproducible production of spacer fabrics damaging of glass fibres has to be avoided. Therefore, take-up and handling of preforms has to take place in a fibre sparing way as well as the weft yarn forces within the weaving process have to be limited.

2 WEAVING PROCESS

To realize the hollow structure shown in Figure 1, the warp yarns are divided into at least two systems. One of these warp yarn systems weaves the upper and lower layers. The other warp yarn system is responsible for weaving of crosslinks. While the first warp yarn system is weaving the upper and lower layers, the warp yarns of the second system are also divided into two parts which are integrated into the upper and lower layers. Only the warp yarns of the second system are weaved into the crosslinks. In the middle of the crosslink, the divided warp yarns of the second system change their sides, which look like a flat “X” in the cross section. During the weaving of crosslink, the warp yarns of the first system build a floating. After finishing the required length of the crosslink, the two warp yarn systems are integrated along couple of weft yarns. Subsequently, a temporary fabric storage is moved into the shed through a special terry weaving mechanism, which gives exactly the length of floating and the height of crosslink. The floatings of the first warp yarn system are pulled back and the woven crosslinks are formed as demonstrated in Figure 2, [4, 5]. For the manufacturing of the hollow spacer structures additional equipment, like an elongated take-up motion, had to be developed.

Figure 2: Principle of weaving technology for spacer fabrics

3 SIMULATION MODEL

During the phase of mechanical design it was necessary to estimate and to restrict the static and dynamic warp thread forces due to the new hybrid yarn and the new spacer fabric geometry. However both are necessary for:

- dimensioning of roller drives of the elongated take-up motion
- avoiding unnecessarily high warp thread forces and fiber damage

Hence and referring to the papers of other authors [6-9] a simulation model for weaving of one layer was developed.

The model predicts the transient interactions between weaving machine (warp beam servo drives, back rest roller, shed, beat-up of reed), yarns and take-up. The components of weaving machines are modeled with inertias, forces and momentums. The threads between the machine components are modeled as spring-damper-elements. Modeling and parameterization of the threads is carried out with so-called characteristic threads. A characteristic thread merges the properties of a set of threads which are going the same path through the machine (same warp beam, same heddle frame). The modeled machine and textile components and the basic model parameters are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Machine components, basic parameters and principle of modeling.

The principle of modelling and simulation is the discretization into spring-damper-inertia systems with concentrated parameters. The rigid bodies of machine components are so-called nodes; the parameter of each node is the inertia $m_{K,i}$ with the node number i . In the example in the upper right corner of Figure 3 a node is represented by the deflection roller with its mass moment of inertia. The nodes are connected with spring-damper elements representing the warp threads. The parameters of each element are the stiffness $c_{E,l,j}$ and the damping $d_{E,l,j}$ with the element number j . At first in each simulation step each node computes with the fluxes of the connected elements which are predicted from the tendency of the last simulation steps (commonly forces resp. momentums $F_{E,l,j}^*$). The following equations are calculated at each node:

$$\ddot{x}_K = \frac{\sum F_E}{m_K} \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{x}_K = \int \ddot{x}_K dt \quad (2)$$

$$x_K = \int \dot{x}_K dt \quad (3)$$

Velocity \dot{x}_K and displacement x_K – which can be translational or angular displacements respectively – will be assigned to the connected elements to calculate the spring-damper force:

$$F_E = c_E \cdot \Delta x_E + d_E \cdot \Delta \dot{x}_E \quad (4)$$

The implementation of the model is realized under MATLAB®-Simulink®.

4 IDENTIFICATION OF YARN PARAMETERS

To predict warp thread forces a number of parameters have to be determined by conducting experiments. One of these parameters regards to the stiffness behavior of the yarn. Standardized tests like the determination of single-end breaking force and elongation at break, according to DIN EN ISO 2062 may be used to characterize the yarn behavior. However, during weaving only a fraction of breaking force is applied to the threads. Under these relatively small forces the yarn shows a different elastic behavior. Therefore an experimental set up was used to determine the force to strain relation in a force range relevant for weaving processes. The test rig allows to apply different loads to a yarn with

a free length of $l_{\text{yarn}}=1$ m. The yarn elongation is measured contactless with a photogrammetric system by taking pictures at every load step, Figure 4.

Figure 4: Experimental set up for the determination of stress-strain-behavior

The spacer fabrics are made of a GF-hybrid yarn with 1870 tex and a glass fiber volume content of 30%. During weaving this material will be processed as a twisted yarn. Figure 5 shows the force to strain diagrams of two types of yarn. The stiffness - which is higher for the non-twisted type - of the yarn shows a nonlinear behavior. In addition to the nonlinearity, the twisted yarn shows a hysteresis. That means that the strain is different for increasing and decreasing loads. When the load direction changes, i.e. in case of a load reversal, the stiffness behavior switches between loading and unloading. Because of this, the measured force-strain relation depends on the applied load profile. With regard to this behavior the yarn model has been expanded by a hysteresis model.

Figure 5: Identification of yarn parameters

In order to model the nonlinear force to strain behavior a third order polynomial approach is used. The hysteresis of the yarn is modeled by an inner friction force, which depends on amount and direction of the effective strain. Parameters were determined by fitting the measured data. Figure 5 also shows the uncertainties of yarn behavior and measured data. The triangles represent the force-strain behavior of four single measurements. The solid lines depict simulations with yarn parameters fitted by a discrete least square approximation.

5 SIMULATION RESULTS

Figure 6 shows simulated forces of four characteristic threads compared to measured forces. The number of the warp thread corresponds to the number of the heddle shaft the thread is connected with. These four threads or heddle shafts respectively belong to the warp yarn system responsible for weaving the lower layer of the spacer perform (cf. Figure 2).

Figure 6: Measured und simulated warp thread forces.

According to weaving pattern, shed geometry, take-up motion and yarn parameters the forces differ for the different characteristic threads. Changes in only one of these parameters will lead to a variation of the forces of all characteristic threads. In Weaving it is necessary that a tensile stress is applied to

any warp thread at any time. On the other side the warp thread forces have to be limited to avoid damaging of fibers. This is especially true, in the case of weaving preforms for the reproducible production of glass fiber reinforced composites. Finding the machine parameters which allow to run the weaving process and the manual customization of these parameters is a time consuming task even for experienced machine operators. This task can be supported by an optimization using the simulation model of the weaving process.

Figure 7 shows the example of the vertical heddle shaft position. The position of shaft 8 not only influences the warp threads related to this shaft, but the forces on heddle shaft 2 as well. Increasing the position only leads the slightly increasing maximum forces. Decreasing the position by 10 mm leads to zero forces and is therefore not tolerable for the weaving process.

Figure 7: Influence of a variation of the vertical position of heddle shaft 8 on the forces of warp threads connected to heddle shaft 2

In this case it seems to be a good choice to reduce the vertical position of heddle shaft 8 by 5 mm. With this position maximum forces can be reduced and zero forces can be avoided. However, Figure 7 only depicts the influence of a single parameter on one warp thread. One has to keep in mind, that for an optimization the range of all warp thread forces has to be considered and that many parameters have to be varied.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The reproducible manufacturing of near-net-shape spacer preforms from glass/polypropylene hybrid yarns requires the limitation of warp thread forces to avoid fibre damage and to guarantee the mechanical properties of the composites made of these preforms. Finding optimized machine parameters is a time consuming task, which can be supported by a simulation model of the weaving process. This can be done by conducting simulation runs under variation of parameters. An ongoing work is to apply optimization algorithms to run this virtual optimization in an automated way. The simulation model can not only be utilized to optimize a given machine configuration. Examples for further fields of application are prediction of warp forces for a different yarn material or determination of the influence of different weaving patterns

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